

About the possible effects of wind and solar power plants and cloud seeding on weather and climate

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Abstract

The atmosphere, with its phenomena, is a thin and vulnerable layer of the Earth that, together with its internal and external environment, is in a temporary state of dynamic equilibrium. This equilibrium changes when the inflow and outflow energies, the physical and chemical components, or other parameters of the system vary, which can be caused by natural processes and anthropogenic activities. This paper discusses solar and wind energy production and cloud seeding, whose current level of application has approached or crossed the threshold where they may contribute to climate change.

Keywords: weather, climate, solar power, wind power, cloud seeding, sustainability

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1 INTRODUCTION

Although the term "dynamic equilibrium" refers to closed systems, and the atmosphere, in terms of its external and internal environment, is open, the inflow and outflow energy vary slowly compared to the internal changes. Therefore, for a sufficiently short period, the time-dependent atmosphere can be considered as a system in a temporary state of dynamic equilibrium (hereafter: state), which, for a given period, can be represented by some characteristic parameters of synoptic and Rossby waves (energy, amplitude, wave number, phase, ...) (Rossby, 1939; Holton and Hakim, 2012).

The state of the atmosphere can be changed by varying the amount of energy entering and leaving the system, as well as the chemical and physical components of the system, which can be caused by natural processes and by anthropogenic activities. Today, thanks to the rapid development of science and technology, humankind has powerful tools at its disposal. At the same time, their brains, individual and collective thinking, decision-making methods, and competitive behavior have not changed much since the age of the caveman (Knickerbocker, 1939; von Neumann and Morgenstern, 1944; Szent-Gyorgyi, 1970).

The energy that enters the atmosphere and drives the meteorological processes is mostly of solar origin and to a lesser extent geothermal and anthropogenic origin. At the same time, some

of the outgoing energy returns to space or is stored temporarily on the Earth's surface as heat, for a short time in vegetation, or for a longer time in fossil fuels as chemical bonds. Almost all of the energy in the atmosphere is provided by the incoming solar energy, which consists primarily of electromagnetic radiation (EMR). Furthermore, this energy, directly and indirectly, drives the biosphere, humanity, society, and even our industry and economy. In addition, the Sun has particle radiation (solar wind) whose effects on the atmosphere are orders of magnitude smaller than the effects of EMR. However, while the intensity of the solar EMR varies by a few percent over the solar cycle, the intensity of the solar wind (space weather) varies significantly. Furthermore, while the incoming EMR affects the illuminated hemisphere of the Earth, the absorption of energetic electron precipitation, induced by the solar wind, occurs in relatively small areas within the polar regions of the ionosphere on the night hemisphere. Although the energy of an electron precipitation event is low compared to atmospheric phenomena of the same base area, it causes ionospheric disturbances that can disturb the balance of underlying atmospheric phenomena, thereby increasing the variability of weather around solar maximum and influencing the state of the atmosphere (Tóth and Szegedi, 2003).

The chemical and physical components that can affect the state of the atmosphere are primarily various gases, aerosols, and water vapor of both natural and anthropogenic origin.

One such group of chemical components is greenhouse gases, which absorb a certain percentage of the long-wave EMR from the Earth's surface, thereby warming the atmosphere and causing global warming (Foote, 1856; Tyndall, 1872). As their concentration has increased significantly in recent centuries due to human activities, the global temperature and energy of the atmosphere have increased, and the general state of the atmosphere has changed (Boergens et al., 2020; UNEP, 2021; IPCC, 2022; Iyer et al., 2022; WMO, 2022).

Aerosols are principal components of the atmosphere that screen out solar EMR and act as cloud condensation nuclei that substantially affect cloud formation and the location of the onset of precipitation relative to the place of initiation of cloud development. At high aerosol concentrations, more and smaller cloud droplets are formed, which, instead of raining down, rise higher, form ice crystals, and carry latent heat, water, and aerosols to higher altitudes. These processes inhibit cloud formation, while clouds can drift downwind from their source, resulting in more precipitation tens or even hundreds of kilometers away. At the same time, areas with natural and anthropogenic sources of aerosol pollution can dry out, leading to dust storms, wildfires, droughts, and even higher aerosol concentrations, which can ultimately be an unstable self-excitation process (Andreae et al., 2004; Rosenfeld et al., 2008; Pringle et al., 2009; Wengenmayr, 2010; Wendisch et al., 2016; Twohy et al., 2021; Zaveri et al., 2022). In this way, aerosols can affect the water cycle, the balance between atmospheric phenomena, and thus the state of the atmosphere, and can contribute to climate change.

Increasingly applied anthropogenic activities, solar and wind energy production, and cloud seeding have some positive results for humankind, but their large-scale application raises questions.

Solar and wind power plants, which are said to be sustainable and renewable, gain significant amounts of energy from the solar EMR and atmospheric flows (IRENA, 2022), which may affect these, and the related processes. Although there are studies on the possible use of wind energy from the jet stream and its possible effects on the atmosphere (Archer and Caldeira, 2009; Miller et al., 2011), there are no focused studies on the increasingly installed solar and wind power plants. However, above a certain level of energy and power, these activities may affect atmospheric processes and phenomena, the balance between them, and thus the state of the atmosphere, and may contribute to climate change.

In cloud seeding, artificial aerosols, called seeding agents, are delivered to the atmosphere to influence precipitation formation for rain and snowfall enhancement, rainfall intensity reduction, hail suppression, fog clearing, and diverting lightning, and are widely used by

government and private organizations, in more than 50 countries around the world (Schaefer, 1968; Lee, 2014). The effects of seeding agents are similar to those of natural and other anthropogenic aerosols in cloud formation and precipitation initialization (Andreae et al., 2004; Rosenfeld et al., 2008; Pringle et al., 2009; Wengenmayr, 2010; Wendisch et al., 2016; Twohy et al., 2021; Zaveri et al., 2022). Therefore, the large-scale and long-term application of cloud seeding may affect the water cycle, the balance between atmospheric phenomena, and thus the state of the atmosphere, and may contribute to climate change.

2 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Today, the long-term and high-level applications of solar and wind power generation and cloud seeding are approaching or exceeding the limits beyond which weather and climate processes can be affected.

2.1 The possible effect of the large-scale application of solar power plants on weather and climate

Both photovoltaic (PV) energy production and photosynthesis (PS) collect light energy, and above a certain level of application, not only photosynthesis but also photovoltaic energy production can affect atmospheric phenomena and processes.

Table 1. Solar power capacity by country and territory (P) in 2021. Estimated areas of solar power plants (A), where the average specific power of mono-Si solar cells $\eta = 140 + (215 - 140) / 2 = 177,5 \text{ W/m}^2$ was used to estimate the areas of solar power plants (A) (see Table 2.1 of (Luther et al., 2014)). The maximum energy that can be produced daily (E).

Country / territory	Solar power capacity by country and territory in 2021 (IRENA, 2022)		Estimated areas of solar power plants (Luther et al., 2014)	Maximum energy that can be produced daily
	P (MW)	(%)	A (km ²)	E (J/day)
China	306 973	36	1 729	2,65E+16
EU	160 382	19	904	1,39E+16
Germany	58 461	7	329	5,05E+15
Italy	22 698	3	128	1,96E+15
Spain	15 952	2	90	1,38E+15
...
United States	95 209	11	536	8,23E+15
Japan	74 191	9	418	6,41E+15
Australia	19 076	2	107	1,65E+15
South Korea	18 161	2	102	1,57E+15
Vietnam	16 660	2	94	1,44E+15
...
World total	849 473	100	4 786	7,34E+16

When sunlight reaches the surface of a solar panel, green plant, or algae, some percentage of it is outside of the suitable frequency band, some reflected, and others absorbed and converted into heat or other forms of energy. This loss is $L_{PV} \approx 88...90\%$ in the case of a solar panel and $L_{PS1} \approx 63\%$ in the case of photosynthesis (Zhu et al., 2008; Capellán-Pérez et al., 2017).

The remaining percentage in the case of a solar panel is the efficiency that for current single and polycrystalline silicon cells on average is $G_{PV} \approx 10...12\%$. This value depends on the physical parameters of the photovoltaic system, reduced by the geographical location, the way

it is mounted, the angle of incidence of the radiation, and the meteorological conditions (Capellán-Pérez et al., 2017). Of the remaining percentage, in the case of photosynthesis in green plants and algae, $L_{PS2} \approx 31...33\%$ is actively used for carbohydrate synthesis and transport processes such as respiration and evapotranspiration, and $G_{PS} \approx 4...6\%$ is the photosynthetic efficiency or the light energy converted and stored in chemical bonds (Zhu et al., 2008).

While photosynthesis interacts with the atmosphere in both passive (L_{PS1}) and active ($A_{PS}=L_{PS2}+G_{PS}$) ways, the interaction of photovoltaic energy production itself is only passive (L_{PV}, G_{PV}). However, due to land use and short-delayed electricity consumption, the generated photovoltaic energy (G_{PV}) becomes active, and a significant part of the extracted energy returns to the environment as heat. Since $A_{PS}>G_{PV}$ and the surface area of green plants and algae is orders of magnitude greater than the estimated surface area of solar panels worldwide, the impact of photovoltaic energy production on atmospheric processes, to a first approximation, is negligible compared to the effects of photosynthesis.

However, each of the three largest solar energy producing territories (China, EU, and USA) can produce as much electrical energy in one day as is already comparable to the energy of a frontal system (Table 1, Fig. 1). This raises the possibility that the recent high and increasing level of photovoltaic energy production, though in a complex and here not investigated way, may affect atmospheric processes and phenomena, which require further investigations.

2.2 The possible effect of the large-scale application of wind power plants on weather and climate

Any of the three largest wind energy producing territories in the Northern Hemisphere (China, EU, and USA) can extract so much energy from the atmospheric flow in one day, which is already comparable to the energy and power of a frontal system (Table 2, Fig. 1).

Table 2. Installed wind power capacity by country and territory (P) in 2021. Estimated areas of wind power plants (A), where the overall average direct impact area of 0,3 ha/MW was used to estimate the areas of wind power plants (A) (see Table 2.1 of (Denholm et al., 2009)). The maximum energy that can be produced daily, or the extracted atmospheric kinetic energy daily (E).

Country / territory	Installed wind power capacity by country and territory in 2021 (IRENA, 2022)		Estimated areas of wind power plants (Denholm et al., 2009)	Maximum energy that can be produced daily
	P (MW)	(%)	A (km ²)	E (J/day)
China	328 973	40	987	2,84E+16
EU	187 497	23	562	1,62E+16
Germany	63 760	8	191	5,51E+15
Spain	27 497	3	82	2,38E+15
France	18 676	2	56	1,61E+15
...				
United States	132 738	16	398	1,15E+16
India	40 067	5	120	3,46E+15
United Kingdom	27 130	3	81	2,34E+15
Brazil	21 161	3	63	1,83E+15
Canada	14 304	2	43	1,24E+15
...				
World total	824 874	100	2475	7,13E+16

This fact is not negligible as the maximum number of simultaneously existing frontal systems is not many since it is related to the number of cyclones, which is related to the wave number

of synoptic and Rossby waves. (Wells, 1997; Vallis, 2006). Although the extracted energy is orders of magnitude smaller than the energy of the general circulation (Table 2, Fig. 1), and the remaining energy is continuously equalized and redistributed among the atmospheric phenomena, the kinetic energies of the affected phenomena, due to the law of conservation of energy, are locally weakened. The situation is further complicated by the fact that a significant portion of the extracted energy, after a short delay, returns to the environment as heat.

Figure 1. Comparison of daily solar and wind energy production with the kinetic energy and mean size of atmospheric phenomena. **Open square:** Kinetic energy and the length scale of atmospheric phenomena (adapted from based on Figure 9.5 of (Wells, 1997)). **Triangle:** Maximum energies that can be produced daily by the largest solar energy producing territories (open triangle) and the “World total” data (filled triangle) in 2021 (see Table 1). **Circle:** Maximum energy that can be produced daily by the largest wind energy producing territories (open circle) and the “World total” data (filled circle) in 2021 (see Table 2).

These activities may even weaken a frontal system and associated cloud formation processes (Table 2, Fig. 1), thereby reducing precipitation and increasing the potential for drought formation in areas of high wind energy production, which phenomenon has been observed (Boergens et al., 2020; Balting et al., 2021; Ionita et al., 2022; WMO, 2022). Above a certain level of energy and power, these activities may affect atmospheric processes and phenomena, the balance between them, and thus the state of the atmosphere, and may contribute to climate change. In addition, these processes may affect the reliability of weather forecasting, which overall requires attention and further study.

2.3 The possible effect of the large-scale application of cloud seeding on weather and climate

In cloud seeding, the commonly applied glaciogenic AgI and raindrop-forming hygroscopic NaI seeding agents are said to be environmentally safe (Curic et al., 2008; Dessens et al., 2016), and their main delivery method to clouds is the application of ground generators due to their simplicity and relatively low cost (List, 2004; Curic et al., 2008; Qiu and Cressey, 2008; Seto

et al., 2012; Lee, 2014; Goenawan et al., 2015; Dessens et al. 2016; Munoz, 2017; Cotton, 2022).

However, even if the delivery method and agent are chosen correctly, it is uncertain whether they will reach the desired region and disperse at the desired concentration. In addition, it is difficult to predict how a cloud will behave and to determine which effects are natural and which are caused by cloud seeding. (Qiu and Cressey, 2008).

In addition, the application of ground-based AgI generators involves a lot of uncertainty; their efficiency is low and requires the emission of large numbers of aerosol particles over a long time (Curic et al., 2008; Cotton, 2022). About 1.1×10^4 kg/year of AgI is used for cloud seeding in more than 50 countries around the world (Table 3) (Schaefer, 1968; Lyday, 2000; Lee, 2014), which is about twice the mass of micrometeoroids entering the atmosphere each year (Rojas et al., 2021), and their concentration can be very high over the seeded areas.

Table 3. Cloud seeding countries in 2014. (on the base of (Lee, 2014))

High extent:	Australia, China, India, Russia, United Arab Emirates, United States, Vietnam
Medium extent:	Argentina, Austria, Brazil, Bulgaria, Canada, Cuba, France, Germany, Greece, Guinea Bissau, Hungary, Iran, Israel, Japan, Jordan, Korea, Mexico, Morocco, Niger, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Spain, Uzbekistan, Venezuela
Low extent:	Algeria, Burkina Faso, Cambodia, Cape Verde, Chad, Chile, Gambia, Indonesia, Iraq, Libya, Malaysia, Mali, Mauritania, Pakistan, Philippines, Senegal, Syria, Thailand, Zimbabwe

Ground generators are installed in large area networks 8-10 km apart. Each generator burns about 1.1 liter/hour of acetic solution of AgI (or AgI-NaI) and occasionally emits about 8.4×10^{15} nanoparticles/hour for hours to a few days (Dessens et al., 2016).

Since the uninfluenced state of the cloud cannot be measured, and there are no measurements above the ground generator networks, the effects of cloud seeding cannot be known with sufficient accuracy. The only way to test different concepts about the related mechanisms involved is a numerical simulation, which shows that the injection of AgI into the target cloud can lead to an enhanced precipitation area at about 40-110 km in the downwind direction from the center of mass of the seeded area (Curic et al., 2008; Qiu and Cressey, 2008; Goenawan et al., 2015; Dessens et al., 2016).

Since these effects are similar to those of aerosols in cloud formation and precipitation initiation, and cloud seeding is already being used on a large scale and for long periods of time, therefore, this activity may shift the location of the onset of precipitation downwind and can cause drought in seeded areas, especially in the high and medium extent countries (Table 3), (Andreae et al., 2004; Rosenfeld et al., 2008; Pringle et al., 2009; Wengenmayr, 2010; Wendisch et al., 2016; Twohy et al., 2021; Zaveri et al., 2022). For example, in the case of a cold front, cloud seeding can, on average, increase precipitation at higher latitudes in the temperate zone, while causing drought at lower latitudes, a phenomenon that has been observed. (Boergens et al., 2020; Balting et al., 2021; Ionita et al., 2022; WMO, 2022).

Therefore, the large-scale application of cloud seeding may affect the water cycle, the balance between atmospheric phenomena, and thus the state of the atmosphere, and may contribute to climate change. It may also affect the reliability of weather forecasting, which requires attention, and further research.

3 CONCLUSIONS

This work relies on freely available sources and draws a simple recognition that the application to a large extent of solar and wind energy production and cloud seeding is currently approaching or may have already reached the level where those can influence atmospheric processes and phenomena (Figure 1, Table 1, Table 2, Table 3). These human activities, at their current level of application, are already able to influence the balance of atmospheric phenomena, may affect the state of the atmosphere, thus the reliability of weather forecasts, and may contribute to climate change. However, it is not easy to test these effects, as this can only be done with simulations or experimentally by systematically switching these activities on and off, which would threaten e.g. the security of energy supply and agricultural production.

This work draws attention to the fact that sustainable development, above a certain level of human intervention, is only possible in a very narrow way, which necessitates the reduction or elimination of the activities discussed above and requires efficient and reduced consumption. Additionally, this work aims to encourage further investigations of these and other human activities that could potentially affect the state of the atmosphere and other parts of our environment.

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